

Mapping the Research on Customer Satisfaction and Loyalty in Online Platforms: A Bibliometric Approach

Marsya Aulia Rizkita¹

Article history:

Received: January 27, 2024; Accepted: March 30, 2024; Displayed Online: April 09, 2024; Published: June 30, 2024

Keywords

First keyword;

Customer Satisfaction;

Customer Loyalty;

Research Trends;

Bibliometric Analysis;

Abstract

Customer satisfaction and loyalty in online platforms is a growing area of research to inform efforts to improve the quality of electronic services. The application of bibliometrics aims to understand global conditions by referring to basic indicators such as the number of annual publications, journal sources, citation frequency, authors, and research hotspots. Document types were limited to journal articles in the Scopus database between 2018 and 2022. Using several inclusion criteria, a total of 46 articles were analyzed. The results of this study show that the number of articles continues to increase gradually and linearly over time. The journals consistently published are the Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services and Cogent Business and Management. The most cited paper was related to website quality attributes and information trust, later identified as hotspot research. This research has provided an overview for conducting meaningful research in the future and helped formulate appropriate policies on electronic marketing.

1. Introduction

Customer satisfaction is an important construct in the current marketing literature (Dash et al., 2021; Zhao et al., 2020). Likewise, customer loyalty is the most pressing issue in the commercial era (Ng & Ng, 2003). Customer satisfaction and loyalty have been linked to various contexts depending on the product or service offered (Dash et al., 2021). It intersects with various levels of customer outcomes (Mittal et al., 2023). This field plays a role in introducing customer input as a driver of customer behavior (Eisingerich et al., 2016).

Due to the rapid development of information and communications technology infrastructure and the diffusion of internet connectivity, organizations have introduced many technology-based services for their customers, including e-services provided by public sector organizations (Hung et al., 2020;

¹Brawijaya University, Malang, Indonesia; marsyarizky@student.ub.ac.id

Khan et al., 2021). The rapid development of internet connectivity diffusion has also encouraged various organizations to introduce electronic-based services to customers in various sectors (Hung et al., 2020; Khan et al., 2021). Information technology is now considered a key component of an organization's running strategy. Meanwhile, in deepening information technology system reform in Indonesia, the government emphasizes several priority policies to utilize digital technology, including ensuring that the digital economy functions for all and building trust in the digital world (Hani, 2021). Apart from this, it should also be noted that the lever for effective information technology-related policies is the availability of high-quality research (Aminullah, 2020).

The COVID-19 pandemic has also forced companies to find new solutions and change how they do business (Carnevale & Hatak, 2020). With changes in people's habits worldwide due to social restrictions and lockdowns, many people are working from home, increasing online platform use (Sheth, 2020). Service-oriented businesses experienced the most drastic strategic and operational changes during the unprecedented pandemic. With the advancement of technology, various organizations are changing from traditional ways and are now focusing on Internet platforms as a service provider medium to improve service quality (Kim-Soon et al., 2014).

The research literature on customer satisfaction and loyalty has been widely studied. Generally, it leads to the statement that customer satisfaction ultimately leads to loyalty to products or services (Utami et al., 2023). Recently, Academicians and practitioners have moved to study customer satisfaction and loyalty in e-service contexts (Al Amin et al., 2023; Ponirin et al., 2016; Rahi & Abd.Ghani, 2019; S. K. Sharma et al., 2017). However, the results of these studies are rarely reported from a bibliometric perspective. Previous systematic studies mostly analyzed customer satisfaction and loyalty in traditional marketing and did not specifically discuss it in the bold context (Hidayat & Budi Utami, 2022; Sánchez-Rebull et al., 2018).

To address this problem, this research was conducted using bibliometric analysis. The main objective is to understand the scope of customer satisfaction and loyalty research worldwide. By examining trends in the number of annual publications in source journals, citation frequency, and the number of contributing authors and research hotspots, sufficient evidence will be obtained for objective comparative analysis regarding the development of bold service quality. In general, applying this method can provide an overview of research hotspots and distribution, which is very important for clarifying what is already known and identifying research deviations.

In addition, because the COVID-19 pandemic has changed consumer behavior in Indonesia and views towards electronic services To address this problem, this research was conducted using bibliometric analysis. The main objective is to understand the scope of customer satisfaction and loyalty research worldwide. By examining trends in the number of annual publications in source journals, citation frequency, and the number of contributing authors and research hotspots, sufficient evidence will be obtained for objective comparative analysis regarding the development of bold service quality. In general, applying this method can provide an overview of research hotspots and distribution, which is very important for clarifying what is already known and identifying research deviations. In addition, because the COVID-19 pandemic has changed consumer behavior in Indonesia and views towards electronic services (Al Amin et al., 2023) the findings of this research are to pay attention to the moderating role of the pandemic and all website and application-based services. The findings of this research are to pay attention to the moderating role of the pandemic and all website and application-based services.

2. Literatur Review

Customer Satisfaction

According to Oliver (1981) in Srivastava & Rai (2018) a consumer's satisfaction refers to a psychological state and is combined with the consumer's feelings about previous brand experiences. Shankar et al. (2003) also define satisfaction as a pleasant perception of service and loyalty as a consumer's commitment to the service provider. Meanwhile, according to Syzmanki & Hise (2000) in Mohammad Ahmad Al-hawari (2015), consumer satisfaction in the online context itself is defined as the cumulative result of one party or someone who has different experiences with a product or service within a certain period.

Consumer satisfaction is about how the company meets consumer expectations, meaning that consumer satisfaction with service quality is based on a comparison between the expected service and the actual service experienced (Q. Zhang et al., 2020). Therefore, consumer satisfaction will occur if the actual service quality exceeds the consumer's perceived expectations. Satisfaction level is a measure of how well consumer needs are met by service providers (Ataburo et al., 2017). If the level of satisfaction felt by consumers is higher, it will result in a more loyal consumer base, thereby positively influencing a company's profitability (Demir et al., 2020). According to Mooradian and Olver (1997) in ("THE THEORY OF EMOTIONS IN MARKETING Ming-Hui Huang," 2001) said that consumer satisfaction also increases the profitability of a company through "word of mouth." An online company's reputation will be destroyed if consumers fail to obtain the necessary information, timely delivery, or inefficient handling of inquiries.

Customer Satisfaction and Loyalty

In marketing, customer satisfaction is often the focus of company strategy. Satisfaction is an individual's response to feelings, namely the extent consumers perceive expectations for a product and service (Sangadji & Sopiiah, 2013). Other researchers say that customer satisfaction is a combined response after someone obtains or consumes a product or service within a certain period (Dash et al., 2021). Satisfaction is theoretically referred to as an assessment of a product and service provided, which is an emotional aspect of consumer loyalty (Cronin et al., 2000). When consumers decide whether or not to switch to a competing brand, they are often guided by feelings of satisfaction or dissatisfaction with the previous brand (He et al., 2012).

Consumer satisfaction and loyalty have a positive relationship (Shankar et al., 2003). Espejel et al. (2008) also confirmed that consumer satisfaction is recognized as the main influence in forming consumers' future purchasing intentions. Satisfied consumers are more likely to tell others about their experiences and thus engage in positive word-of-mouth advertising (Yeh et al., 2016). Consumer satisfaction is cognitive and emotional; these two things jointly participate in the formation of satisfaction because feelings are an important component of the experience (del Bosque & San Martín, 2008). Consumers show satisfaction with a brand when introducing it adds to their positive image within a social group, or when a sense of belonging to the social group is achieved (He et al., 2012). Consumers often demonstrate intense emotional connections with brands. The consumer-brand relationship is so deep that it influences consumer behavior in various ways, such as using a particular brand for life, even to the extreme, and getting a company logo tattooed on their body. Thus, Empirical studies show that brand love produces positive outcomes, such as loyalty and willingness to pay high prices.

(He et al., 2012) said that lifestyle consists of values, tastes, and consumption patterns. Lifestyle greatly impacts consumers' consumption behavior and brand preferences (Cătălin & Andreea, 2014). The more a brand image fits a consumer's lifestyle, the higher the level of satisfaction with the brand experience. Therefore, marketers need to ensure they can develop consumer satisfaction with the brand by creating a brand that is commensurate with consumers' lifestyles (Yeh et al., 2016). When

customers' expectations of a product or service match reality, they will feel satisfied, otherwise they will feel disappointed (Oktareza et al., 2020).

For a company, once customers recognize their products or services and have a certain psychological dependence (Cui, 2014), they will also actively recommend trusted products and carry out word-of-mouth publicity (Akbari & Wagner, 2021). Therefore, repeat purchases and word-of-mouth recommendations have become important indices for measuring customer loyalty (Q. Zhang et al., 2020). Especially when companies face adverse external environments such as buyers' markets, loose customer relationships, and increasing competitive pressure, customer loyalty will demonstrate an important strategic position (Rai & Srivastava, 2014). External loyalty performance includes share measures, repeat purchase behavior, etc. However, researchers prefer to use behavioral scales to improve customer loyalty, such as how environmental changes affect customer behavioral loyalty (Aghamolaei et al., 2014; Jarideh, 2016).

From a company development perspective, customer loyalty is an important factor influencing a company's success and profitability, so companies often consider customer loyalty a critical goal of their long-term development (Rai & Srivastava, 2014). In other words, customer loyalty seems invisible but has great commercial value. Considering ways of building relationships of satisfaction and loyalty that promise to improve a company's performance and economic value, it is not worrying that this phenomenon is a growing research topic.

3. Materials and Methods

Bibliometric methods have been widely used in all research to quantitatively analyze the descriptive characteristics of various journals (Roemer & Borchardt, 2015). The advantage of this method is that it can analyze thematic and research trends over time from various academic literature in a more insightful manner (Tu et al., 2022). Another prominent advantage of this method is that it can provide information regarding authors (Durán Sánchez et al., 2014), leading journals (Martínez-López et al., 2018), research topics (Blanco-Mesa et al., 2017), and others.

Database and Study Literature

We collect data from Scopus the largest accurate database covering the world (Baas et al., 2020). A research period of five years was chosen because it is sufficient to understand the progress and trends of research on customer satisfaction and loyalty towards online platforms in general. We apply parameters from January 1, 2018, to December 31, 2022. Research on online platforms emerged and surged in the 2019 time period (COVID-19 pandemic) so it needs to be included in order to provide more valuable findings when conducting bibliometric analysis. Apart from that, a systematic study of customer loyalty was carried out for the period 2004-2017 (Valipour et al., 2018), so this research tries to provide further research. Thus, the search history that we carried out is: TITLE-ABS-KEY (online AND service AND quality AND customer AND loyalty) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar")) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English")) AND (LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA , "Spark Plug") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA , "COMP") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA , "ECON")) AND (LIMIT-TO (PUBSTAGE , "final")) AND (LIMIT-TO (OA , "all")) AND (LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2023) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2022) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2021) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2020) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2019) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2018)).

In this study, we used the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analysis (PRISMA) model referring to Page et al. (2021). The inclusion points applied are as follows. (1) articles only research/original type; (2) articles written in English; (2) the article's field of study is business, management, accounting, computer science, economics, econometrics, and finance; (3) the

article has been published and is open access; (4) articles published between 2018 and 2022; (5) the article is only related to satisfaction and loyalty research. The exclusion criteria used are: The order of inclusion that we carried out is presented briefly in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Systematic review procedure using PRISMA

Based on the PRISMA model (Figure 1), an initial search in the Scopus database yielded 579 articles. There were 403 journal articles included in the original or research category, in other words there were 176 articles that were excluded because they were published in the form of proceedings, book chapters, and Erratum as well as review articles, short communications, and others. Based on the language used, there were only seven articles in Chinese, Spanish, German, Korean and Malaysian, resulting in 396 articles. The next step is to use criteria related to the subject, there are 352 relevant articles and of them only 93 articles can be accessed in full text or open access. Next, we published articles published before 2018 and 2023 to obtain 69 articles. In the final step, we rechecked the abstracts and main texts of the remaining articles, finding 23 articles that did not meet the criteria. The final result of this series of selection was 46 articles.

Analisis bibliometrik menggunakan VOSviewer

The data obtained is saved in *CSV and *RIS format which is then synchronized into Reference Manager (Mendeley). After comparing the advantages of several software, VOSviewer was selected as the tool that best suited the data set of this study. This software has the ability to collect data from various scientific data bases, such as Scopus and reference manager files, such as RIS files (van Eck & Waltman, 2010). VOSviewer has been used in economics and business (Castillo-Vergara et al., 2018) and can extrapolate and create networks of publications, researchers, keywords, and/or terms (Martins et al., 2022).

4. Results and Discussions

This bibliometric analysis provides an overview of customer satisfaction and loyalty research trends in the context of the dare platform from 2018 to 2022 and provides an interpretation of the research based on a global perspective. This article has an interesting contribution because the bibliometric method used is not only based on basic indicators such as keywords, authors, main and

most cited journals, but also displays research focus and themes based on keyword clusters. Thus, the results can provide insight into research hotspots and boundaries.

Yearly Publication Trends

The number of articles published in the five year period (2018-2022) shows a growth trend. In 2018 and 2019, only 8 and 6 articles were published. In 2020 the increase more than doubled, with 15 articles. In 2021 and 2022 there will be an increase, namely 18 and 19 articles. Thus, it is stated that articles related to customer satisfaction and loyalty in the context of platforms dare to double from 2018 to 2022. The publication trend is almost linear, not exponential, relatively stable, and continues to increase gradually over five years (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Yearly Publication Trends (2018-2022)

During the 2020 pandemic, the overall number of publication metrics was lower than in 2019 (Gao et al., 2021). However, this decline is not general, many publications in several scientific disciplines actually show an increase, one of which is in the fields of bold platforms and business. The pandemic has given rise to new topics because it has had a major impact on the economic and business sectors (Kuipers et al., 2022). Globally, the pandemic has brought bold and inevitable growth in platform usage (Wang et al., 2021). Consumers are increasingly reducing direct contact and moving to online contact (Tran, 2021).

The Main Publication

Based on the visual analysis of co-journals shown in Figure 3, it can be seen that there are two journals that are dominant and have consistency in publishing this theme, namely the Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services (JRCS) and Cogent business and management (CBM). Based on the impact factor and quartile values published by the Journal Citation Report (JCR), it shows that JRCS was published by Elsevier Ltd. with an H index of 104 it is in Quartile 1. The SJR score in 2018 was 1.21 and increased gradually every year until it was at a score of 2.26 in 2021. Judging from the number of documents, this journal published a total of 178 articles in 2018, half of the articles

published in 2021 there were 425 articles. The total citations were 1953 in 2018 and increased exponentially to 8161 in 2021.

Meanwhile, CBM (H Index 23) published by Cogent OA is in Quartile 2 with an SJR value in 2021 of 0.41 and has almost doubled compared to 2018 with a score of 0.22. The number of documents published in 2021 is 230 articles out of 499 over the last three years. Total citations in 2018 were only 210 citations and will increase approximately sixfold in 2022 to 1296 citations.

Figure 3. Journals of publications in Customer Satisfaction and Loyalty in Online Platforms.

The co-journal approach also shows the relationship between each journal that publishes on the theme of customer satisfaction and loyalty to the bold platform. This concentration refers to the division of the same journal based on the subject of content. Interestingly, the two main journals (JRCS and CBM) identified are in the same cluster as the "sustainability" journal. It is inevitable that the increase in bold use of platforms has brought ecological impacts and brought about unsustainable development (Settey et al., 2021). In a business model, it is said to be successful in the economic dimension when digital platform users feel the desire (Kolk & Ciulli, 2020). Sustainability has also become a theme in marketing communications that is much more important than before in the last decade (Sahadev et al., 2022).

Then, in the other two clusters the focus is more on the categories "data", "information", and "technology". The use of technology in marketing is very important and has provided sufficient evidence to increase customer satisfaction (Sleiman et al., 2021). Physical locations can move to online locations with the use of technology is an important goal, and this can have an impact on increasing performance and productivity (ElFarmawi, 2023). In general, information technology has an important role in increasing excellence and changing the current business environment (Awamleh & Ertugan, 2021).

Most Cited Articles

The five published and most cited articles on the theme of Customer Satisfaction and Loyalty on Online Platforms are presented in Table 1. Overall, these five articles were published from 2018 to

2021, with a total of 378 citations, with citations per paper and per year amounting to 75.60. Meanwhile, the number of people per paper was 4.20 with an h-index and g-index of 5.

Three of the five most cited articles were published in JRCS and CBM. Most widely referenced is the article published in JRCS entitled "Investigating the antecedents of customer brand engagement and consumer-based brand equity in social media" written by Algharabat et al. (2020), with a total of 127 citations. This research attempts to research customer brand engagement as a multidimensional construct. The results show that customer brand involvement can be predicted by the roles of consumer involvement, consumer participation, and brand self-expression. Another interesting finding is that activation has an impact on brand loyalty. However, brand awareness does not affect brand loyalty.

Followed by an article by Shahid Iqbal et al. (2018) with the title "The impact of self-service technology (SST) service quality on customer loyalty and behavioral intentions: The mediating role of customer satisfaction" published in CBM with a total of 87 citations. This research reveals that there is a positive relationship between service quality, loyalty and intention behavior through customer satisfaction. It was explained that these results were useful for increasing consumer satisfaction and loyalty. The third article that is widely cited with a total of 71 citations is the article with the title "Factors that Influence Customer Satisfaction and Loyalty in Online Food Delivery Services during the COVID-19 Pandemic: Relation to the Open Innovation Model" written by (Prasetyo et al., 2021), and published in the Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity. This research shows that hedonic motivation can influence customer satisfaction followed by information quality. Another important finding is that, usability factors such as perceived ease of use and navigation design do not influence customer satisfaction and loyalty.

Furthermore, there is research conducted by Shafiee & Bazargan (2018) on customer loyalty behavior in online shopping: The role of e-service quality and e-recovery. This article was published in the Journal of Theoretical and Applied Electronic Commerce Research and has been published 51 times. This research explains that information security and website performance can influence service quality. Meanwhile, responsiveness and contact positively influence e-recovery, and at the same time can influence online repurchase.

Finally, the fifth position was also published in CBM in 2018 with the title "Effect of Employee Empathy on Customer Satisfaction and Loyalty During Employee-Customer Interactions: The Mediating Role of Customer Affective Commitment and Perceived Service Quality." This article was written by Bahadur et al., (2018) with a total of 42 citations. This research investigates the indirect influence of employee empathy on customer loyalty through an intervening variable, namely customer satisfaction. The result is that employee empathy has a positive and indirect effect on customer loyalty.

Table 1. Most cited articles in Customer Satisfaction and Loyalty in Online Platforms

No	Title	Authors	Year	Publication	Cites / year	Cites/ paper
1	Investigating the antecedents of customer brand engagement and consumer-based brand equity in social media	Raed Algharabat, Nripendra P. Rana, Ali Abdallah Alalwan, Abdallah Baabdullah & Ashish Gupta	2020	Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services	42.3 3	127.00

2	Impact of self-service technology (SST) service quality on customer loyalty and behavioral intention: The mediating role of customer satisfaction	Muhammad Shahid Iqbal, Masood Ul Hassan & Ume Habibah	2018	Cogent Business & Management	17.4 0	87.00
3	Factors Affecting Customer Satisfaction and Loyalty in Online Food Delivery Service during the COVID-19 Pandemic: Its Relation with Open Innovation	Yogi Tri Prasetyo, Hans Tanto, Martinus Mariyanto, Christopher Hanjaya, Michael Nayat Young, Satria Fadil Persada, Bobby Ardiansyah Miraja & Anak Agung Ngurah Perwira Redi	2021	Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity	35.5 0	71.00
4	Behavioral customer loyalty in online shopping: The role of e-service quality and e-recovery	Majid Mohammad shafiee & Negin Ahghar Bazargan	2018	Journal of Theoretical and Applied Electronic Commerce Research	10.2 0	51.00
5	Effect of employee empathy on customer satisfaction and loyalty during employee-customer interactions: The mediating role of customer affective commitment and perceived service quality	Waseem Bahadur, Saira Aziz & Salman Zulfiqar	2018	Cogent Business and Management	8.40	42.00

Most Collaborating Authors

Highlighting the interconnection of top authors in publications on the theme of customer satisfaction and loyalty on online platforms in Figure 4, it can be seen that there are eight authors who are interconnected between the time span 2019 to 2021. Vo N. T. is the author who connects older articles (2019) with newer ones (2021). The dominant author as a reference is Sharma.

Figure 4. Authors With The Most Collaborations

This visual representation also shows that there are four writers/researchers who are dominant on this theme, and they are related to each other, namely Aziz, Syams, Abdur Rehman, and Osman. The four of them have maximum social interaction with other writers. The identified authors have made major contributions to various studies, especially on sharia insurance (takaful) consumers. Takaful means responsibility or guarantee and is based on the principle of sharing (al-Musharakah) (Billah, 2019; Ghlamallah et al., 2021). In other words, takaful shows shared responsibility, collective guarantee, and joint effort (Maduku & Mbeya, 2023).

There are two articles written by four dominant authors. First, the article is entitled "Revisiting corporate image through service quality and relationship marketing: empirical evidence from Takaful customers in Malaysia and Saudi Arabia". This research examines the combination of relationship marketing dimensions and service quality as predictors of corporate image and customer loyalty through corporate reputation in the context of sharia insurance. In addition, this research compares perceived service quality and marketing relationships from the customer perspective of two countries, namely Malaysia and Saudi Arabia (Abdur Rehman et al., 2021).

The second, not much different from the first article, work entitled "Let's get acquainted: an empirical study of takaful customer service provider relationships from a Saudi Arabian perspective" also tests the combination of relationship marketing dimensions and service quality as significant predictors of corporate image. However, more narrowly, the scope of this research is only from the perspective of Saudi Arabian customers (Osman et al., 2022).

The Main Research Topic

This research can also explain the research hotspots of customer satisfaction and loyalty on online platforms in five years (2018-2022) through keyword centrality. Clustering diagram with two main keywords "customer satisfaction" and "customer loyalty" shows the frequency and centrality of the words. Additionally, the larger the dot, the higher the word frequency. Keywords with quite high frequency and word centrality are "service quality" and "e-service quality".

the database shows that the authors who contributed the most were Aziz, Shams, Abdur Rehman, and Osman, who researched takaful in Saudi Arabia and compared it with Malaysia.

By using bibliometric methods to analyze research in the field of marketing strategy related to customer satisfaction and loyalty, research trends and contributions of authors, journals, and articles, and key research hotspots can be easily identified. This bibliometric method can display research progress in the field of customer satisfaction and loyalty, so that it can help future researchers to find research visibility that needs to be filled, and help stakeholders to formulate appropriate policies. Another strength of this work is that it covers the COVID-19 pandemic and includes rapid research due to the very high use of bold services, so the results can lead to more comprehensive research. This also makes it possible to carry out larger empirical research regarding breakthroughs in increasing customer satisfaction and loyalty towards service quality on the bold platform, but still in line with the desired aspects.

There are several limitations that must be considered from this research. This research is only based on the Scopus database and within the last five years (2018-2022). The findings of this study do not necessarily represent the full range of customer satisfaction and loyalty in the context of bold services outside the Scopus database and time frames before and after the period. Additionally, the inclusion of research articles during the COVID-19 pandemic could bias research trends and bias findings. For this reason, we are trying to carry out observations and analysis over a longer period of time in the future.

Acknowledgements

This manuscript has no conflict of interest. The author delivers her gratitude to the reviewers and the publisher who have helped him in publication processes.

References

- Abdur Rehman, M., Khan, S., Osman, I., Aziz, K., & Shams, G. (2021). Revisiting the corporate image through service quality and relationship marketing: An empirical evidence from Malaysian and Saudi Arabian Takaful customers. *Journal of Islamic Accounting and Business Research*, 12(6), 849–871. Scopus. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JIABR-05-2020-0140>
- Aghamolaei, T., Eftekhaari, T. E., Rafati, S., Kahnouji, K., Ahangari, S., Shahrzad, M. E., Kahnouji, A., & Hoseini, S. H. (2014). Service quality assessment of a referral hospital in southern Iran with SERVQUAL technique: Patients' perspective. *BMC Health Services Research*, 14, 322. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1472-6963-14-322>
- Akbari, K., & Wagner, U. (2021). Playing When Paying and What Happens Next: Customer Satisfaction and Word-of-Mouth Intention in Gambled Price Promotions. *Schmalenbach Journal of Business Research*, 73(2), 243–271. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41471-021-00110-y>
- Al Amin, Md., Muzareba, A. M., Chowdhury, I. U., & Khondkar, M. (2023). Understanding e-satisfaction, continuance intention, and e-loyalty toward mobile payment application during COVID-19: An investigation using the electronic technology continuance model. *Journal of Financial Services Marketing*. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41264-022-00197-2>
- Algharabat, R., Rana, N. P., Alalwan, A. A., Baabdullah, A., & Gupta, A. (2020). Investigating the antecedents of customer brand engagement and consumer-based brand equity in social media. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 53. Scopus. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2019.01.016>
- Aminullah, E. (2020). STI policy and R&D governance for the attainment of SDGs: Envisioning the Indonesia's future. *Asian Journal of Technology Innovation*, 28(2), 204–233. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19761597.2020.1722187>
- Ataburo, H., Muntaka, A. S., & Quansah, E. K. (2017). Linkages among E-Service Quality, Satisfaction, and Usage of E-Services within Higher Educational Environments. *International Journal of Business and Social Research*, 7(3), 10–26. <https://doi.org/10.18533/ijbsr.v7i3.1040>
- Awamleh, F., & Ertugan, A. (2021). The Relationship Between Information Technology Capabilities, Organizational Intelligence, and Competitive Advantage. *SAGE Open*, 11(2), 21582440211015200. <https://doi.org/10.1177/21582440211015201>
- Baas, J., Schotten, M., Plume, A., Côté, G., & Karimi, R. (2020). Scopus as a curated, high-quality bibliometric data source for academic research in quantitative science studies. *Quantitative Science Studies*, 1, 1–10. https://doi.org/10.1162/qss_a_00019
- Bahadur, W., Aziz, S., & Zulfiqar, S. (2018). Effect of employee empathy on customer satisfaction and loyalty during employee–customer interactions: The mediating role of customer affective commitment and perceived service quality. *Cogent Business and Management*, 5(1), 1–21. Scopus. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2018.1491780>
- Billah, M. M. (2019). *Islamic Insurance Products: Exploring Takaful Principles, Instruments and Structures*. Springer International Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-17681-5>
- Blanco-Mesa, F., Merigó, J. M., & Gil-Lafuente, A. M. (2017). Fuzzy decision making: A bibliometric-based review. *Journal of Intelligent & Fuzzy Systems*, 32(3), 2033–2050. <https://doi.org/10.3233/JIFS-161640>

- Blut, M., Chowdhry, N., Mittal, V., & Brock, C. (2015). E-Service Quality: A Meta-Analytic Review. *Journal of Retailing*, 91(4), 679–700. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretai.2015.05.004>
- Carnevale, J. B., & Hatak, I. (2020). Employee adjustment and well-being in the era of COVID-19: Implications for human resource management. *Journal of Business Research*, 116, 183–187. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2020.05.037>
- Castillo-Vergara, M., Alvarez-Marin, A., & Placencio-Hidalgo, D. (2018). A bibliometric analysis of creativity in the field of business economics. *Journal of Business Research*, 85, 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2017.12.011>
- Cătălin, M. C., & Andreea, P. (2014). Brands as a Mean of Consumer Self-expression and Desired Personal Lifestyle. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 109, 103–107. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2013.12.427>
- Cronin, J. J., Brady, M. K., & Hult, G. T. M. (2000). Assessing the effects of quality, value, and customer satisfaction on consumer behavioral intentions in service environments. *Journal of Retailing*, 76(2), 193–218. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-4359\(00\)00028-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-4359(00)00028-2)
- Cui, L. N. (2014). *Bank Retail customer loyalty Management Research*. [Master Thesis]. Heilongjiang University in China.
- Dash, G., Kiefer, K., & Paul, J. (2021). Marketing-to-Millennials: Marketing 4.0, customer satisfaction and purchase intention. *Journal of Business Research*, 122, 608–620. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2020.10.016>
- del Bosque, I. R., & San Martín, H. (2008). Tourist satisfaction a cognitive-affective model. *Annals of Tourism Research*, 35(2), 551–573. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.annals.2008.02.006>
- Demir, A., Maroof, L., Sabbah Khan, N. U., & Ali, B. J. (2020). The role of E-service quality in shaping online meeting platforms: A case study from higher education sector. *Journal of Applied Research in Higher Education*, 13(5), 1436–1463. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JARHE-08-2020-0253>
- Durán Sánchez, A., Álvarez-García, J., & Del Río-Rama, M. de la C. (2014). *Active Tourism Research: A Literature Review (1975-2013)*. <https://ruc.udc.es/dspace/handle/2183/14503>
- Eisingerich, A., Merlo, O., Heide, J., & Tracey, P. (2016). Customer Satisfaction and Purchase Behavior: The Role of Customer Input. In C. Campbell & J. (Jonathon) Ma (Eds.), *Looking Forward, Looking Back: Drawing on the Past to Shape the Future of Marketing* (pp. 220–220). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-24184-5_57
- ElFarmawi, W. (2023). Leveraging Technology to Improve Business during and after the Pandemic. *International Journal of Business, Technology and Organizational Behavior (IJBTOB)*, 3(1), Article 1. <https://doi.org/10.52218/ijbtob.v3i1.258>
- Espejel, J., Fandos, C., & Flavián, C. (2008). Consumer satisfaction: A key factor of consumer loyalty and buying intention of a PDO food product. *British Food Journal*, 110(9), 865–881. <https://doi.org/10.1108/00070700810900585>
- Gao, J., Yin, Y., Myers, K. R., Lakhani, K. R., & Wang, D. (2021). Potentially long-lasting effects of the pandemic on scientists. *Nature Communications*, 12(1), Article 1. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-021-26428-z>

-
- Ghلامallah, E., Alexakis, C., Dowling, M., & Piepenbrink, A. (2021). The topics of Islamic economics and finance research. *International Review of Economics & Finance*, 75, 145–160. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iref.2021.04.006>
- Hani, A. (2021, August 15). Indonesia Adopts Digital Tech Policies for an Inclusive Future—OpenGov Asia. *OpenGov Asia*. <https://opengovasia.com/indonesia-adopts-digital-tech-policies-for-an-inclusive-future/>
- He, H., Li, Y., & Harris, L. (2012). Social identity perspective on brand loyalty. *Journal of Business Research*, 65(5), 648–657. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2011.03.007>
- Hidayat, M. S. & Budi Utami. (2022). Three Years Journal of IJSTM (International Journal of Science Technology & Management: Inarah): A Bibliometric Analysis. *International Journal of Science, Technology & Management*, 3(1), 167–178. <https://doi.org/10.46729/ijstm.v3i1.431>
- Hung, S.-Y., Chen, K., & Su, Y.-K. (2020). The effect of communication and social motives on E-government services through social media groups. *Behaviour & Information Technology*, 39(7), 741–757. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0144929X.2019.1610907>
- Jarideh, N. (2016). The Investigation of Effect of Customer Orientation and Staff Service-Oriented on Quality of Service, Customer Satisfaction and Loyalty in Hyperstar Stores. *International Journal of Science and Research (IJSR)*, 5(3), 1837–1841. <https://doi.org/10.21275/v5i3.18031604>
- Khan, S., Umer, R., Umer, S., & Naqvi, S. (2021). Antecedents of trust in using social media for E-government services: An empirical study in Pakistan. *Technology in Society*, 64, 101400. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techsoc.2020.101400>
- Kim-Soon, N., Ahmad, A. R., & Ahmed, M. (2014). E-Service Quality in Higher Education and Frequency of Use of the Service. *International Education Studies; Vol. 7, No. 3; 2014*, 7, 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ies.v7n3p1>
- Kolk, A., & Ciulli, F. (2020). The potential of sustainability-oriented digital platform multinationals: A comment on the transitions research agenda. *Environmental Innovation and Societal Transitions*, 34, 355–358. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eist.2019.12.008>
- Kuipers, S., van der Wilt, A., & Wolbers, J. (2022). Pandemic publishing: A bibliometric review of COVID-19 research in the crisis and disaster literature. *Risk, Hazards & Crisis in Public Policy*, 13(4), 302–321. <https://doi.org/10.1002/rhc3.12262>
- Maduku, D. K., & Mbeya, S. (2023). Understanding family takaful purchase behaviour: The roles of religious obligation and gender. *Journal of Financial Services Marketing*. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41264-023-00213-z>
- Martínez-López, F. J., Merigó, J. M., Valenzuela-Fernández, L., & Nicolás, C. (2018). Fifty years of the *European Journal of Marketing*: A bibliometric analysis. *European Journal of Marketing*, 52(1/2), 439–468. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EJM-11-2017-0853>
- Martins, J., Gonçalves, R., & Branco, F. (2022). A bibliometric analysis and visualization of e-learning adoption using VOSviewer. *Universal Access in the Information Society*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10209-022-00953-0>
- Mittal, V., Han, K., Frennea, C., Blut, M., Shaik, M., Bosukonda, N., & Sridhar, S. (2023). Customer satisfaction, loyalty behaviors, and firm financial performance: What 40 years of research tells us. *Marketing Letters*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11002-023-09671-w>
-

- Mohammad Ahmad Al-hawari. (2015). How the personality of retail bank customers interferes with the relationship between service quality and loyalty. *International Journal of Bank Marketing*, 33(1), 41–57.
- Mukonza, C., & Swarts, I. (2020). The influence of green marketing strategies on business performance and corporate image in the retail sector. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 29(3), 838–845. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.2401>
- Ng, V., & Ng, I. (2003). Customer Loyalty on Recurring Loans. In J. Liu, Y. Cheung, & H. Yin (Eds.), *Intelligent Data Engineering and Automated Learning* (pp. 653–660). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-540-45080-1_88
- Noor, N., Rao Hill, S., & Troshani, I. (2022). Recasting Service Quality for AI-Based Service. *Australasian Marketing Journal*, 30(4), 297–312. <https://doi.org/10.1177/18393349211005056>
- Oktareza, M. E. T., Halin, H., & Handayani, S. (2020). The Effect of Service on Customer Satisfaction at PT Pandu Siwi Sentosa. *International Journal of Community Service & Engagement*, 1(01), Article 01.
- Osman, I., Abdur Rehman, M., Mohy Ul Din, S., Shams, G., & Aziz, K. (2022). Let's get acquainted: An empirical study on takaful customer-service provider relationships from Saudi Arabian perspectives. *Journal of Islamic Marketing*, 13(11), 2209–2231. Scopus. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JIMA-06-2020-0175>
- Page, M. J., McKenzie, J. E., Bossuyt, P. M., Boutron, I., Hoffmann, T. C., Mulrow, C. D., Shamseer, L., Tetzlaff, J. M., Akl, E. A., Brennan, S. E., Chou, R., Glanville, J., Grimshaw, J. M., Hróbjartsson, A., Lalu, M. M., Li, T., Loder, E. W., Mayo-Wilson, E., McDonald, S., ... Moher, D. (2021). The PRISMA 2020 statement: An updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *BMJ*, 372, n71. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.n71>
- Pérez, A., & Rodríguez del Bosque, I. (2015). How customers construct corporate social responsibility images: Testing the moderating role of demographic characteristics. *BRQ Business Research Quarterly*, 18(2), 127–141. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.brq.2014.04.003>
- Phonthanukitithaworn, C., Naruetharadhol, P., Wongsachia, S., Mahajak, N., & Ketkaew, C. (2021). Identifying the relationship between Travel Agent's Web Service Quality and E-brand Reputation. *Cogent Business & Management*, 8(1), 1999784. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2021.1999784>
- Ponirin, Scott, D., & Von Der Heidt, T. (2016). E-Loyalty: Its Antecedents, Implications and Differences between Developed and Developing Countries. In D. Sharma (Ed.), *Cultural Perspectives in a Global Marketplace* (pp. 77–82). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-18696-2_29
- Prasetyo, Y. T., Tanto, H., Mariyanto, M., Hanjaya, C., Young, M. N., Persada, S. F., Miraja, B. A., & Redi, A. A. N. P. (2021). Factors affecting customer satisfaction and loyalty in online food delivery service during the COVID-19 pandemic: Its relation with open innovation. *Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity*, 7(1), 1–17. Scopus. <https://doi.org/10.3390/joitmc7010076>
- Rahi, S., & Abd.Ghani, M. (2019). Integration of DeLone and McLean and self-determination theory in internet banking continuance intention context. *International Journal of Accounting & Information Management*, 27(3), 512–528. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJAIM-07-2018-0077>

-
- Rahman, M., & Yunus, M. (2014). *Green Marketing for Creating Awareness for Green Consumerism*. 3, 18–22. <https://doi.org/10.18034/gdeb.v3i1.167>
- Rai, A. K., & Srivastava, M. (2014). Customer loyalty in Indian aviation industry – An empirical examination – UUNZ. *Asia Pacific Journal of Business and Management*, 5(1), 44–59.
- Riko Cahyo Pribadi, Abdul Rivai, & Suharto. (2020). The effect of emotional marketing and marketing strategy on purchase decisions through consumer satisfaction as a mediation variables in PT. Nureka Bintang Abadi. *Global Journal of Engineering and Technology Advances*, 5(3), 123–128. <https://doi.org/10.30574/gjeta.2020.5.3.0119>
- Roemer, R. C., & Borchardt, R. (2015). *Meaningful metrics: A 21st century librarian's guide to bibliometrics, altmetrics, and research impact*. Association of College and Research Libraries, A division of the American Library Association.
- Sahadev, S., Muralidharan, S., & Singh, P. (2022). Introduction to the special issue on marketing communications and sustainability. *Journal of Marketing Communications*, 28(3), 227–231. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13527266.2021.1942145>
- Sánchez-Rebull, M.-V., Rudchenko, V., & Martín, J.-C. (2018). The antecedents and consequences of customer satisfaction in tourism: A systematic literature review. *Tourism and Hospitality Management*, 24(1), 151–183. <https://doi.org/10.20867/thm.24.1.3>
- Sangadji, E. M., & Sopiah. (2013). *Perilaku Konsumen Pendekatan Praktis disertai: Himpunan Jurnal Penelitian* (Yogyakarta). Andi. [//digilib.usm.ac.id%2Ffek%2Findex.php%3Fp%3Dshow_detail%26id%3D2247](http://digilib.usm.ac.id%2Ffek%2Findex.php%3Fp%3Dshow_detail%26id%3D2247)
- Settey, T., Gnap, J., Beňová, D., Pavličko, M., & Blažeková, O. (2021). The Growth of E-Commerce Due to COVID-19 and the Need for Urban Logistics Centers Using Electric Vehicles: Bratislava Case Study. *Sustainability*, 13(10), 5357. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13105357>
- Shafiee, M. M., & Bazargan, N. A. (2018). Behavioral customer loyalty in online shopping: The role of e-service quality and e-recovery. *Journal of Theoretical and Applied Electronic Commerce Research*, 13(1), 26–38. Scopus. <https://doi.org/10.4067/S0718-18762018000100103>
- Shahid Iqbal, M., Ul Hassan, M., & Habibah, U. (2018). Impact of self-service technology (SST) service quality on customer loyalty and behavioral intention: The mediating role of customer satisfaction. *Cogent Business and Management*, 5(1). Scopus. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2018.1423770>
- Shankar, V., Smith, A. K., & Rangaswamy, A. (2003). Customer satisfaction and loyalty in online and offline environments. *International Journal of Research in Marketing*, 20(2), 153–175. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-8116\(03\)00016-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-8116(03)00016-8)
- Sharma, S. K., Govindaluri, S. M., Al-Muharrami, S., & Tarhini, A. (2017). A multi-analytical model for mobile banking adoption: A developing country perspective. *Review of International Business and Strategy*, 27(1), 133–148. <https://doi.org/10.1108/RIBS-11-2016-0074>
- Sheth, J. (2020). Impact of Covid-19 on consumer behavior: Will the old habits return or die? *Journal of Business Research*, 117, 280–283. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2020.05.059>
- Sleiman, K. A. A., Cai, X., Lan, J., Lei, H., & Liu, R. (2021). Relationship Marketing and Information Technology's Impact on Customer Satisfaction and Commitment. *Open Journal of Business and Management*, 9(3), Article 3. <https://doi.org/10.4236/ojbm.2021.93055>
-

- Srivastava, M., & Rai, A. K. (2018). Mechanics of engendering customer loyalty: A conceptual framework. *IIMB Management Review*, 30(3), 207–218. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iimb.2018.05.002>
- THE THEORY OF EMOTIONS IN MARKETING Ming-Hui Huang. (2001). *Journal of Business*, 16(2), 239–247.
- Tran, L. T. T. (2021). Managing the effectiveness of e-commerce platforms in a pandemic. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 58, 102287. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2020.102287>
- Tu, J., Lin, X., Ye, H., Yang, S., Deng, L., Zhu, R., Wu, L., & Zhang, X. (2022). Global research trends of artificial intelligence applied in esophageal carcinoma: A bibliometric analysis (2000-2022) via CiteSpace and VOSviewer. *Frontiers in Oncology*, 12, 972357. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fonc.2022.972357>
- Utami, B., Hidayat, M. S., & Setyariningsih, E. (2023). The Relationship between Customer Satisfaction and Loyalty: A Systematic Literature Review. *International Journal of Social Service and Research*, 3(1), 54–62. <https://doi.org/10.46799/ijssr.v3i1.222>
- Valipour, A., Noraei, M., & Kavosh, K. (2018). A meta-analysis of customer loyalty in the banking Services. *ASEAN Marketing Journal*, 10(2), 137–155.
- van Eck, N. J., & Waltman, L. (2010). Software survey: VOSviewer, a computer program for bibliometric mapping. *Scientometrics*, 84(2), 523–538. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-009-0146-3>
- Wang, C.-N., Dang, T.-T., & Nguyen, N.-A.-T. (2021). Outsourcing Reverse Logistics for E-Commerce Retailers: A Two-Stage Fuzzy Optimization Approach. *Axioms*, 10(1), 34. <https://doi.org/10.3390/axioms10010034>
- Yeh, C. H., Wang, Y. S., & Yieh, K. (2016). Predicting smartphone brand loyalty: Consumer value and consumer-brand identification perspectives. *International Journal of Information Management*, 36(3), 245–257. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2015.11.013>
- Zhang, N. (2022). How does CSR of food company affect customer loyalty in the context of COVID-19: A moderated mediation model. *International Journal of Corporate Social Responsibility*, 7(1), 1. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40991-021-00068-4>
- Zhang, Q., Cao, M., Zhang, F., Liu, J., & Li, X. (2020). Effects of corporate social responsibility on customer satisfaction and organizational attractiveness: A signaling perspective. *Business Ethics*, 29(1), 20–34. <https://doi.org/10.1111/beer.12243>
- Zhao, Y., Wen, L., Feng, X., Li, R., & Lin, X. (2020). How managerial responses to online reviews affect customer satisfaction: An empirical study based on additional reviews. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 57, 102205. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2020.102205>